

Load-Bearing Bioresorbable Nanocomposites (LBBN), Izp-2025/1-0364

Version 1

Description

The LBBN (Low-temperature Bioresorbable Bone Nanocomposites) project generates multidisciplinary research data to support the development of sustainable bioresorbable materials for paediatric bone repair. The data collected and produced will encompass materials synthesis, structural and chemical characterisation, mechanical testing, and biological evaluation.

The primary data types include:

- Experimental data from synthesis and processing of CMC/OCP composites (e.g., compositions, processing parameters, raw measurements).
- Analytical data from characterisation techniques (e.g., XRD, FTIR, SEM, mechanical testing).
- Biological performance data from in vitro assays (e.g., cytocompatibility, degradation profiles).
- Computational or derived data used for material optimisation and statistical analysis.

All data will be stored in open, non-proprietary formats whenever possible.

Sensitive or proprietary information (e.g., unpublished results, personal data of researchers) will be handled according to institutional and EU data protection regulations.

Once validated and published, datasets will be deposited in recognised open-access repositories such as Zenodo or institutional repositories, with DOI assignment for citation and reuse.

The DMP will be a living document, updated throughout the project to reflect data collection progress, repository selection, and access conditions. Through transparent and responsible data management, LBBN aims to ensure that its outcomes—supporting sustainable, resorbable biomaterials—remain reproducible, shareable, and beneficial to the broader scientific and medical community.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS LBBN

Grant

Researchers

Janis Locs (0000-0003-3162-7431)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Load-Bearing Bioresorbable Nanocomposites \(LBBN\), IZP-2025/1-0364](#)

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Organizations:

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Contact: [Locs Janis \(janis.locs@rtu.lv\)](mailto:locj@rtu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [LBBN](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2026-03-01](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

Research data sets obtained during project implementation

This dataset will include all relevant data planned for publication under the framework of the Project.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data is being collected in order to confirm the purity of the synthesised materials and test the materials developed.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

100

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes, we have considered re-using of any existing data, however in our case it does not apply.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data in this dataset might be useful to other researchers, e.g., material scientists, chemists, chemical engineers, biomedical engineers, biologists, computational chemists and computer modelling experts, as well as industry R&D specialists, and to anyone interested in calcium phosphate and biomaterial physicochemical property characterization and understanding.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Metadata will include measurement parameters of the data included in the dataset described in readme.txt text file.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Due to the potential of Intellectual Property protection data will not be made open, but with a restricted access upon reasonable request.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Embargo period for data access will be set due to the possibility of creation of Intellectual Property worth protecting via patent application.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

Zenodo is one of the most popular repositories in Europe for any type of data. It is not restricted to specific datasets or fields. Project team already have experience of using it.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

No special tools, generally available software capable of opening data file formats mentioned in 1.1.3.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The expected data formats are XML, TXT, PDF, CSV, XLS.

These data formats can be open using following softwares:

XML - any text editor,

TXT - any text editor,

PDF - any open source web browser, e.g., Firefox,

CSV - any text editor,

XLS - open-source suite that supports XLS spreadsheets, e.g., Apache OpenOffice Calc.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2029-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Janis Locs (0000-0003-3162-7431)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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